

Pan-island network for animal disease control- workshop report

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Summary

All the islands involved operate under unique circumstances, but similarities exist and there is potential for collaborative working.

Lewis & Harris have renewed interest in community working and believe together they can achieve a good level of animal disease control. Challenges include,

- a lack of control over animals moving onto the islands, (multiple ports of entry)
- limited vet services for diagnostics and treatment, vet service staffing
- sourcing investment required for improved port infrastructure.

Orkney has a well-supported livestock industry and want to address sheep scab on the islands. The agriculture industry faces challenges including,

- the need to monitor and control imported animals arriving from the mainland,
- the need for a new slaughterhouse on the islands,
- a training requirement for dipping and dipping licences.

Shetland livestock producers have a robust process in place to control imported animals via the Shetland Animal Health Scheme. A bylaw put in place in July 2024 supports diagnostics and treatment of animals. They have fewer challenges but need to remain vigilant about potential incursions and identified the following,

- there are a limited number of diagnostic tests available,
- there can often be a long turnaround in obtaining diagnostic test results,
- high lab costs for test results can be prohibitive for some producers,
- lack of producer engagement with communal and collaborative activities.

Together the island representatives identified potential areas of collaboration that can be put in place over the coming months. Future opportunities to meet, both online and face to face, will help further strengthen the collaboration and allow for the identification of new areas where connections can be made.

Introduction

Long term, in-depth, research and engagement with stakeholder representative of Lewis and Harris, Shetland and Orkney by researchers from JHI and MRI on the topic of animal health and disease control on Scottish islands (Figure 1) has been ongoing since 2022. Albeit that work was undertaken independently on the three islands there was an interest and desire to investigate an initiative where they could discuss opportunities for inter-island collaborative working.

Figure 1 Participants hard at work at the Pan-Island Workshop

In February 2025, livestock production representatives (farmers, crofters, vets, and other stakeholders) from the island groups for Orkney, Shetland, and Lewis and Harris gathered in Inverness for a two day ‘Pan-Island Workshop’ to share their experiences around animal disease control, with a focus on the disease sheep scab, which is caused by infestation with the ectoparasitic sheep scab mite (Figure 2). The meeting was hosted by the James Hutton (JHI) and Moredun Institutes (MRI) and funded by EPIC Scotland and the Scottish Government Strategic Research Programme (SRP).

The workshop was opened by Claire Hardy from JHI and included a welcome address by Katy Scott, a Policy Officer from the Scottish Government Animal Health and Welfare Division. Stew Burgess from MRI and Niamh Mahon from JHI provided updates of the progress of the project to date. The meeting then took an interactive and participatory approach, focusing on multiple concurrent discussion sessions in island (Lewis & Harris, Shetland and Orkney) and ‘industry sector’ groups (producers, vets, researchers, and pharmaceutical industry). Discussions initially concentrated on group introductions and conversations to understand the unique challenges each of the islands face. The

conversations then moved on to thinking about potential question areas around tighter intra- and inter- island collaboration; how could this benefit the islanders? How can animal disease control be improved? and how could it be coordinated? The final day of the workshop focused on developing visions for the future of animal health on each of the islands and planning actions that would aid the islanders in reaching these goals.

Figure 2 Participants hard at work at the Pan-Island Workshop

Activities

The two-day workshop encouraged lively discussions around the themes of challenges and solutions in managing animal disease control for the islands (Figure 3). This took place both formally, during the workshop activities and informally over the group lunches and the evening meal. Each island group has its own unique context, described in brief in the following section.

Island demographics, topography and infrastructure summaries

Lewis and Harris: one continuous island 38.6 km (24 mi) off mainland Scotland (Figure 3A). It forms part of the Outer Hebrides.

- Livestock are kept in 400+ crofts (mainly tenanted) arranged in Townships
- The most numerous farmed animals are sheep (~30,000) and cattle (~500)
- The land on Lewis is predominately shallow soil supporting rough grazing, some of the in-bye land is improved grassland
- Each croft generally has in-bye land and access to common grazing
- Most families have access to multiply crofts due to inheritance or via the purchase of additional crofts

- Traditional crofters have more than one job – often crofting is not their main source of income
- Lewis and Harris have three ports of entry (Tarbert; Stornoway; Leverburgh)
- No livestock movements on or off the island are recorded
- No lairage for animals if ferries are delayed
- There are no routine diagnostics or treatments of livestock entering the islands
- Lewis and Harris is serviced by one vet practice, currently with one vet (Old Mill Veterinary Practice)
- The islands have a seasonal mart in Stornoway (sales August to October)
- The abattoir in Stornoway, is council run and operates between August and Christmas, with the local vet attending during this period.

Figure 3A. Map of Lewis and Harris

Orkney: The Orkney archipelago (Figure 3B) is located 16 km (9.9 mi) north of mainland Scotland and comprises over 70 islands and skerries, of which 20 have permanent settlements.

- Outer islands are connected to the main island by ferry services
- Three main ports connect Orkney to the mainland (Stromness; Kirkwall; St. Margaret's Hope)
- There are no additional transport records for animals coming to the islands
- There are no diagnostic checks or routine treatments for imported animals
- The agriculture units are generally farms of a range of sizes, there are some owner-occupied crofts
- The land can support mixed agriculture, growing a small amount of limited crops for home use and as a cash crop
- Cattle are the main farmed animal (~23,000), sheep are used to manage the land and are often not a priority
- There is some common grazing available on Hoy, and sheep on North Ronaldsay are grazed on the foreshore

Figure 3B. Map of the Orkney islands

- The islands are serviced by two vet practices (Flett & Carmichael and Northvet)
- The island livestock market is in Kirkwall.
- The islands have no abattoir.

Shetland: Shetland is situated 209 km (130 mi) north of mainland Scotland consisting of 100 islands, 20 of which are occupied Figure 3C.

- The landscape has few trees and acid soils support peatland and rough grazing
- There are crofts with common grazings, but also larger farms with cattle, sheep and crops
- In 2023 the Shetland islands Council reported 4,600 cattle and 290,000 sheep
- The island has an abattoir, in 2022 it reported 3,600 sheep, 360 cattle and 310 pigs were slaughtered
- Lerwick has a mart which sold 75,600 animals through the ring in 2022
- All imported animals arrive in customised containers on the NorthLink ferries to the port at Lerwick
- The Shetland Animal Health Scheme (SAHS) monitors all imported livestock
- Movements are recorded and animals arriving are monitored for certain key diseases
- SAHS provides a screening service for the following diseases at the point of entry: for sheep: Maedi Visna (MV), caseous lymphadenitis (CLA), enzoonotic abortion of ewes (EAE), and sheep scab and for cattle: Bovine viral diarrhoea (BVD) and Johne's
- A new bylaw (2024) requires all sheep to be dipped prior to travelling to their new holding
- The islands are supported by one vet practices, with three locations (Shetland VetsLerwick, Bixter and Scalloway)

Figure 3C. Map of the Shetland islands

Island Successes and Challenges

For the group from **Lewis and Harris** there was a recognition of the successes disease control initiatives including sheep scab, roundworms and liver fluke (figure 4). For example the sheep scab control work saw; the co-ordination of scanning and dipping carried out by the Lewis & Harris Sheep Producers Association (LHSPA); renewal of communal working; more involvement of youngsters (at the mart, stock judging & a newly rejuvenated Young Crofters group); increased general social events (renewed interest in social meetings) and growing interest in animal health. However, concerns exist (figure 4) about the lack of control over animal movements on and off the island. There is currently no lairage provision at the harbour and ferry journeys can be cancelled with little notice, due to weather and seasonal demand. When combined with the fact that the carriage of livestock is at the discretion of the ferry captain, this means that animals can often be transported to the ferry only to find that they cannot travel (even when booked). As there are animal handling/holding facilities there is the potential for significant welfare issues whilst new travel arrangements can be organised. Stakeholders also reported a current lack of interest from the local council in animal disease control. The large amount of common grazing results in mixing of flocks and therefore disease control is difficult to manage. Monitoring all livestock arriving on the islands for disease status and making treatments where necessary is a high priority. Limited vet services have become an issue and needs immediate attention if monitoring and treatment of disease is to be initiated. There may also be a need for improved infrastructure for animal movement and disease monitoring on the island in the future.

Figure 4 Notes written by participants during the workshop activities

For the group from **Orkney** there was a recognition of the previous disease control and eradication successes in the beef sector, local council interest in animal health issues, and a strong culture of working together. One format that has worked well for the agriculture community on Orkney over the years is the Orkney Agriculture discussion group which was established in 1923 and is one of the oldest farming discussion groups in the UK. This group comes together regularly (fortnightly in winter) with the objective to promote the study and development of agriculture and provides a good source of

knowledge, peer to peer exchange and promotes the uptake of innovations. Nevertheless, the Orcadian group were concerned about the marginality of sheep on the Orkney islands. They noted they have more than 23,000 cattle so sheep are considered as the 'lesser' important livestock animal, for many, in terms of the economy. They are often not given priority on the farm, being used to manage grazing and make money.

Farmers do recognise that sheep scab is an issue, that can and should be brought under control. Over 45,000 sheep have been dipped recently by private contractors and on farm dipping, however a coordinated effort is required. Funding for training, particularly for dipping and licences for dip-disposal are required. The lack of common grazing on Orkney is a huge positive as there is less mixing of flocks. However without financial incentive to control sheep diseases, some sheep keepers might be reluctant to join an initiative, and the lack of control over animal movements on and off the islands is a concern. Unlike Shetland, but similar to Lewis and Harris, Orkney has multiple ferries where animals can be imported without control. Although monitoring animal movement onto the northern island groups would be relatively easy to be put in place, those coming from the mainland would require more procedures, including legislation. Although sheep scab control is currently being considered they were aware of other diseases that require managing. They also noted that no abattoir on Orkney resulted in limited surveillance data being available promptly following slaughter. In addition there is the welfare issue of animals being transported to Dingwall from fat sales. The potential for transporting disease due to additional movements and the economic costs of the double transport of livestock down to Dingwall and the carcasses then being transported back were all concerning as well as impacting on sustainability and productivity.

The **Shetland** group recognised the benefits of tight control over animal movements on and off their islands and the advantages of their current infrastructure for testing and treating bought-in animals for a variety of diseases. This group were looking to the future to develop stronger legislation, secure long-term, sustainable funding for animal health, and improve available testing for animal disease. They recognised they were vulnerable to incursions and were aware of the need to remain vigilante. They noted the lack of diagnostic test availability can hamper efforts to monitor incoming livestock. Prompt results from diagnostic labs were essential to ensure the effective monitoring of animal diseases.

Solutions

Everyone present recognised each island situation is very different (Figure 5), however similarities and solutions were identified that could work for the other island communities. Although the group acknowledged there were few animal movements between the islands, and little formal collaboration between them to date, they recognised the value of future inter-island communication and collaboration. This would

be especially useful between key island ‘coordinators’ – roles that are already filled by individuals on Orkney and Shetland and that are currently desperately needed in Lewis and Harris. The group identified that each island had their own livestock producer groups (e.g., the Orkney Livestock Association, LHSPA) that could be leveraged in the future to share messages and coordinate actions. Online meeting platforms could be used to facilitate regular intra- and inter- island conversations.

Discussions between likeminded industry sectors, vets and livestock producers led to interesting conversations that helped develop draft plans around animal disease control implementation. Discussions were focused on practical measures that would work for the island communities farming in remote locations, often with limited resources. There was a recognition of the power and benefit of coming together in-person at this meeting

Figure 5 Maps of each of the island groups with notes by the islanders

to address key issues and support each other to develop tailor-made solutions for each island community.

Sheep producers felt that they could work together and with other groups (e.g., local vets) to get other farmers interested and involved in animal health and managing animal diseases. The training they would like, around disease control methods, specifically dipping and dip disposal, could be provided by vet practices and the research experts. One of the producers has already requested that the transcripts from the presentation on sheep scab should be made available in bite size (watchable) sections (10 mins max) with a recorded audio to be shared to the wider producers. It is hoped this format will help bring the wider more remote producers on board with developing a sheep scab protocol to control sheep scab on the remote islands of Orkney. These resources will be provided for all sheep producers in all the islands.

Researchers thought that they could act as facilitators for pan-island communication, as well as sharing information and acting as a potential source of funding for knowledge exchange activities. Experts would provide access to resources and new Virtual Tours for Orkney and Lewis and Harris will be co-developed to produce a resource for stakeholder engagement and to approach funders. A discussion, on outreach potentials would be explored for future island trips, between the research Institutes. The outreach will be tailored for sharing information with schools and communities.

The **wider sheep industry** on the islands could work to better support producer initiatives and take a big picture approach to actions, thinking at the island scale, and communicating more with Scottish government. All islands will communicate with their Members of the Scottish Parliament to provide information on their current status and potential initiatives to give better control of animal disease. In Lewis and Harris they will communicate with their local council to give a fuller picture of animal disease control and the livestock industry on the islands in general. For inter-island collaboration, Shetland offered support and guidance on approaching the local Council and the Scottish Government regarding getting by-laws compiled and generating interest in creating new policies to enable movement control, monitoring and access to funding. Shetland can also provide information on how to leverage funding from energy companies. This would be an ongoing collaboration for all island groups.

The **vet representatives** identified and discussed many challenges they encounter operating in an island context and potential solutions. Of paramount importance was how to attract, recruit and retain new staff. Access to locum staff is crucial, but competition is high and attracting locums can also be challenging, there are cost implications with operating with locums over a long period of time. Students can help to bridge some of these gaps, thus providing excellent training opportunities for student vets. Funding and facilitating student experiences in island settings where accommodation is often required can be difficult. Succession planning requires facilitation to enable ageing vets to plan in advance, future proofing the service for their clients. No succession plans are currently in place in Lewis & Harris and help could be offered to guide the process. Shetland had a very good transition with a long handover period, which represents an excellent model for succession in other areas, and advice could be offered. Many of the island vets are time constrained largely due to the geography of the islands and remoteness. Clients can be remotely located and travel, although subsidised, is still difficult to achieve. The demographic of the client base is very diverse and quite different from the mainland. Vets provide a service for a range of clients from hobbyists, generational crofters, lifestyle crofters, younger crofters coming through who are often more proactive and larger farms. All of these stakeholders can have very different demands and expectations for their veterinary support. Interaction with the preparing for sustainable farming (PSF) scheme has been patchy across the islands.

Lewis and Harris did a lot of work with the sheep scab blood testing, other island practices struggled with the amount of additional paperwork, the funding model and the time it took (in some cases) to receive results back from certain labs. Certainly more could be made of this opportunity, and this will be important in the future as the farm payment systems develop further – better to embrace it now and encourage early adoption of this type of system. Currently there is very little contact between island vets, however all present were keen to see this improved. Those present liked the idea of establishing a WhatsApp group and could see the benefits in terms of disease awareness, coordination of locums and support cover. There may also be a role for the Highlands & Islands Veterinary Services Scheme (HIVSS) to provide further support on this.

Outcomes

The islanders from each island group developed ‘Future Visions’ for animal disease control on their islands (figure 6) –

For **Lewis and Harris** this involved developing a paid coordinator role for animal health,

which is currently lacking on the island. In addition, it would be useful to gain a better understanding of the scale and scope of animal movements on and off the island from the three ports, and the ability to continue the sheep scab control activities in a way that is sustainable in the long term. Finding a means to fund future activities is high on their priorities list with a report on a business case pending.

For **Orkney** this included, developing a simple island-wide sheep scab control programme that includes testing and dipping, greater engagement with the local council that works towards putting a sheep scab by-law in place, and gaining greater control over animal movements on and off the

Figure 6 Sharing thoughts and ideas at the workshop

islands.

For **Shetland** this involved securing and diversifying sources of funding for on-going animal health schemes, working to increase communal working and community engagement on animal health topics, and a greater focus on breeding replacements so the islands rely less on imported animals. The group decided future meetings both online and in person would be beneficial to build a legacy network to continue the discussions

and maintain and build a sustainable, resilient livestock production sector for the Scottish islands.

Feedback on the workshop

Participants were asked to complete a Slido word cloud to capture their reflections on the workshop in a few words (Figure 7). It was interesting to see the prevailing word was support with the feeling that together the group would be able to provide support to each other. Limited was also captured, the group feeling was that the representatives present were only a small number of interested bodies. We discussed how we could expand the group and increase the impact of the initiative. Several organisations were identified that could be asked to collaborate. Participants offered help to identify contacts and organise links. In addition, it was discussed whether other island groups might be interested in joining the initiative and would benefit from the collaborative working being fostered in the network.

Figure 7: Word cloud developed by participants interacting with the digital app, Slido

Feedback forms filled in by the islanders on the last day of the workshop capture some of the positive feeling that developed in the room over the two days. The forms also highlight areas the participants want to focus on in the future as the pan-island network develops. Figure 8 below are some anonymous quotes from the islanders –

Figure 8: Quotes from workshop participants

Next Steps

The group decided additional meetings would be useful. An initial online meeting is planned at the end of May 2025. Participants also identified many would attend the Royal Highland Show in June, an opportunity for a face to face catchup meeting during the show would be welcomed. Moredun will host the event on their stand on the Thursday. A winter online meeting is envisaged with a final face to face gathering in February.

Additional organisations, islands and individuals that would enhance the group will be identified and contact details shared. Widening membership of the group will help bring in other interested bodies that can add to the collaborative working.

There are two virtual tours being developed one for Orkney and one for Lewis and Harris. These will widen peoples understanding of the context of animal disease control in the islands.

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